

Protocol for product specification and quality control for PGI/PDO protection under EU framework and labels for the valorisation of food products and identity

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Short Description	
<p>This deliverable includes two draft protocols for product specification and quality control for PGI/PDO protection under the EU framework and labels for the valorisation and identity of food products. In particular, a single document has been drafted for the proposal of a PGI in Morocco, concerning extra virgin olive oil produced in the Beni Mellal geographical area, as described in the deliverable itself. For the preparation of the protocol, several olive oil samples of different producers from the identified area were analysed by UNIBO and ENAM to evaluate their main quality and compositional parameters. The results obtained were useful to define some specific characteristics for this product, necessary to develop a product specification document.</p> <p>Regarding Teff flour from Ethiopia, a draft protocol has been outlined based on the information available in the literature and on some analyses carried out by UoM on Teff flour samples from the described area.</p>	
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1. Introduction

1.1 Regulation on PDO/PGI geographical indications in Europe

The European Union's (EU) quality policy for agricultural and food products serves as a fundamental pillar in its efforts to safeguard distinctive regional food traditions while also fostering agricultural diversity and enhancing consumer confidence. This policy framework includes several essential certification schemes, each designed to protect and emphasize unique product qualities linked to geographical origin and traditional practices. The most prominent among these are the Protected Designation of Origin (PDO), Protected Geographical Indication (PGI), and Traditional Specialty Guaranteed (TSG) (Glogoveţan & Pocol, 2024).

The PDO and PGI designations differ in the degree to which the raw materials or production processes are connected to the region where they are produced. Thanks to EU regulations on intellectual property rights, products registered as Geographical Indications (GIs) are legally safeguarded against imitation and misuse within the EU, as well as in non-EU countries that have established reciprocal protection agreements. This prevents unauthorized production or marketing of products under those names. Additionally, product names from outside the EU can also be registered as GIs if their country of origin has a bilateral or regional agreement with the EU that includes mutual protection of such names.

According to the Regulation EU 2024/1143 the term "*traditional*" refers to the documented historical use of a name by producers within a community over a period sufficient for knowledge to be passed down from one generation to the next. This period must be at least 30 years, and such usage may include adaptations made necessary by evolving hygiene, safety standards, and other relevant practices.

The EU's geographical indications system safeguards the names of products originating from specific regions that possess unique qualities or have a reputation tied to their place of production. The distinctions between PDO and PGI primarily concern the proportion of raw materials that must be sourced from the area or the extent to which the production process must occur within that specific region.

- a) Protected designation of origin (PDO): PDO products are those that maintain the closest ties to their region of origin. This designation covers a range of items, including foods, agricultural products, and wines. To qualify as a PDO, every step—production, processing, and preparation—must take place within the specific region; as for labelling, it's mandatory for food and agricultural products, though optional for wine (Figure 1a).
- b) Protected geographical indication (PGI): PGI status focuses on the connection between a product and its geographic region, emphasizing qualities, reputation, or characteristics that are closely tied to its origin. PGI products include foods, agricultural goods, and wines. For most products to qualify, at least one stage—whether production, processing, or preparation—must take place within the

region; when it comes to labelling, it's required for food and agricultural products, but optional for wines (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. a) Protected Designation of Origin logo; b) Protected Geographical Indication logo (https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/farming/geographical-indications-and-quality-schemes/geographical-indications-and-quality-schemes-explained_en#logos).

On 13 May 2024, the new regulation on Geographical Indications (GIs) for wine, spirits, agricultural products, as well as Traditional Specialties Guaranteed (TSG) and optional quality terms for agricultural products came into force, bringing with it several important updates to the existing system. The new regulation aims to strengthen and improve the GI system in several ways. First, it introduces a single, unified legal framework for all three sectors—food, wine, and spirits. By merging different rules governing GI procedures and protection, the regulation streamlines the registration process, making it simpler and quicker for producers to get their products recognized under GI status. In addition, the new rules provide stronger protection for GIs, especially in cases where they are used as ingredients in processed products or sold online. The regulation also enhances protection in the domain name system, ensuring that GI names are better safeguarded from misuse in digital spaces. The updated regulation also recognizes the importance of sustainability. Producers will now have the opportunity to highlight their environmental, economic, and social sustainability efforts. For example, producer groups can make certain sustainable practices mandatory for their products, with these practices included in the product specifications. Furthermore, producers can voluntarily submit a sustainability report, which will be published by the European Commission, offering greater visibility to their sustainability actions. Lastly, the new regulation empowers producer groups by establishing a voluntary system for recognized GI producer groups, which will be set up by EU countries. These groups are given more authority to manage, enforce, and develop their GIs, strengthening their position within the value chain and helping them maintain a competitive edge in the market. Overall, these changes aim to modernize and enhance the GI system, making it more efficient, sustainable, and protective for producers, while also ensuring that consumers continue to benefit from high-quality, authentic products.

As part of the EU's intellectual property rights framework, product names registered as Geographical Indications (GIs) are legally protected from imitation and misuse within the EU, as well as in non-EU countries that have signed specific protection agreements.

Each EU member state's relevant national authorities are responsible for ensuring the protection of these registered names within their territories. They must also act to prevent and stop the illegal production or sale of products that misuse these names.

Non-EU product names can also be registered as GIs if their country of origin has a bilateral or regional agreement with the EU that includes mutual protection for such names. Several non-EU countries, including Colombia and South Africa, have successfully protected the GI names of their products (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Registered PDO or PGI from non-European countries (Figure has been constructed by the extrapolation of data from Glview, <https://www.tmdn.org/giview/gi/search>, accessed on 14th of November 2024).

It is possible to find information on GIs registered in the Union through eAmbrosia (<https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/eambrosia/geographical-indications-register/>), the official EU GI database. Additionally, both EU and non-EU GIs that are covered under protection agreements can be viewed on the Glview portal (<https://www.tmdn.org/giview/>).

Table 1. Elements required by the EU regulation 2024/1143.

Element required	Description
Name to be protected	The name that needs protection as a designation of origin or geographical indication, as used in trade or common language in historically relevant languages of the specific product's geographical area.
Description of the product	Includes details about the product, its raw materials (if applicable), and its primary physical, chemical, microbiological, or organoleptic characteristics.
Definition of the geographical area	Specifies the boundaries of the geographical area where the product is produced or originates.
Evidence of product origin	Provides evidence that the product comes from the defined geographical area.
Method of obtaining the product	Describes the method used to obtain the product, including any local and traditional methods. Information about packaging is included if justified by the applicant group.
Link between quality/characteristics and area	Establishes the connection between the quality or characteristics of the product and the geographical environment. For PDO, this may involve details about the soil, landscape, and human factors. For PGI, it's about the link between product characteristics and geographical origin.
Authorities or bodies for compliance	Provides the name and address of authorities or, if available, bodies responsible for verifying compliance with the product specification.
Specific labelling rules	Lists any unique labelling rules applicable to the specific product in question.

The single document must outline the key details of the product specification. This includes the name to be registered as a designation of origin or geographical indication,

a description of the product (which may also cover specific rules on packaging and labelling), and a clear definition of the geographical area where the product is produced. the document should provide an explanation of the link between the product and the geographical environment or origin, this includes, where applicable, details about the product's characteristics or production methods that demonstrate the connection to the region.

1.2 Regulation on PDO/PGI geographical indications in Europe Importance of PDO/PGI certification for food products and their value enhancement in the European market

This policy framework is vital for supporting rural economies by assisting local producers and protecting the environment. It also plays a key role in consumer protection, ensuring both the quality and authenticity of products. Additionally, these labels help guide consumer decisions, offering confidence about the quality and origin of what they purchase. The EU's implementation of these quality schemes highlights its dedication to upholding high food standards, regional authenticity, and transparency for consumers. As the global market grows and consumer tastes shift, these certifications have become essential for highlighting the distinctiveness of European agricultural and food products. They reflect the union of tradition, quality, and diversity that defines the agricultural heritage of the EU. Therefore, understanding the importance and impact of these labels is crucial not only for regional producers and the agricultural sector but also for consumers who place increasing value on authenticity and quality in their food choices (Glogoveţan & Pocol, 2024). GIs play a dual role: for consumers, they provide quality and reliable information, while for producers, they support rural development and the preservation of traditional methods. By enhancing the reputation of a product, GIs can create a premium market, leading to higher prices and increased income, especially benefiting small-scale producers in rural areas. Consumers value GIs and are often willing to pay more for them. However, the success of GIs in promoting rural development depends on various factors like social, economic, and environmental conditions. While GIs can help increase agricultural sustainability, they are not a guaranteed path to success. Local actors must consider additional factors such as cooperation and institutional support to achieve the desired outcomes (Cei et al., 2018).

GIs also play a crucial role in preserving traditional production methods and cultural heritage. Many GIs are rooted in age-old recipes or techniques that have been handed down through generations. By safeguarding these practices, GIs help ensure that they are not lost or replaced by more modern, industrial approaches (WIPO, 2021).

Another socio-economic benefit of GIs is their ability to generate employment and drive economic growth. In a food market that is becoming more industrialized and standardized, GI labels can assure consumers of a more authentic, distinctive, and higher-quality product (Broude, 2005). For producers, GIs offer a chance to differentiate their products and potentially command higher prices (Deselnicu et al., 2013). By creating a premium market, GIs can attract investment and generate new jobs, especially in rural areas. They establish a strong link between the product and the geographical

region where it originates, making GIs a powerful marketing tool that draws consumers' attention to these regions. Since many of these regions are rural, GIs offer vital opportunities for local development. Protecting GIs can help sustain economic activities and promote settlement in rural areas, improving the living standards of residents. The rural population stands to benefit the most from these products in terms of increased income and job creation. Additionally, while rural areas often face challenges in gaining a competitive advantage through technology or costly advertising, GIs provide an alternative by signalling to consumers that the product comes from a specific region and possesses certain qualities. This does not require significant investment in technology or marketing (Deselnicu et al., 2013).

However, it is challenging to obtain a clear and consistent understanding of the impacts of PDO and PGI on social and economic sustainability. A review of international literature on the socio-economic impacts of GIs examined the benefits of GIs from perspectives such as quality signalling, market access, and rural development. It also identified traditional knowledge and biodiversity as potential goals that could be supported by the GI system. While the review emphasizes the potential benefits of GIs, it notes that much of the discussion around these socio-economic advantages remains conceptual due to a lack of empirical evidence. The review also highlights the difficulties in realizing these potential benefits, particularly in developing countries. It points out that GI laws alone do not guarantee the desired socio-economic outcomes. The challenges faced by GIs in developing countries show that, in addition to robust legal protection tailored to the local context, the GI process requires support from relevant institutions and policies. It is widely acknowledged that significant benefits are linked to GIs (Bramley, 2011). Achieving these dynamics is not a straightforward process, as it depends on how the GI system is implemented, protected, and utilized. This requires coordinated efforts from both governments and producers. Developing countries must recognize that the socio-economic effects of GIs are highly context-dependent, and the impact may differ from one country or product to another (Grote, 2009). While GIs offer an appealing policy tool with the potential for significant benefits, it is up to each country to carefully assess the expected advantages and challenges within their specific context and for their unique products (Bramley, 2011). In conclusion, GIs can lead to a wide range of socio-economic impacts.

1.3 Objectives

Nutritional imbalances are a growing concern in Africa, with African diets and traditional foods struggling to penetrate markets, whether in African cities or across Europe. A major challenge lies in the inadequate implementation of food safety standards, lack of quality control along the value chain, and the absence of harmonized food labelling. These issues create significant barriers to the valorisation of novel African products and their access to global markets. However, protecting African food products under designations such as PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) or PGI (Protected Geographical Indication) could be a game-changer, offering a powerful pathway to enhancing their value on the European market. By adhering to strict food safety standards, ensuring

quality control throughout the value chain, and harmonizing labelling practices, African food products can gain credibility and recognition, unlocking new opportunities for growth and market expansion globally.

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2. Olive oil (virgin/extra virgin)

2.1 Protocol for a Moroccan extra virgin olive oil product specification and quality control for PGI/PDO protection under EU framework and labels for the valorisation of food products and identity

2.1.1. Single document

[Huile d'olive extra vierge Dir Béni Mellal]

1. Name(s) [of Protected Designations of Origin (PDO) or Protected Geographical Indications (PGI)]

“Huile d'olive extra vierge Dir Béni Mellal”

2. Geographical indication type

PDO PGI

3. Third Country to which the defined geographical area belongs

Morocco

4. Description of the agricultural product

4.1. Classification of the agricultural product in accordance with the Combined Nomenclature heading and code, as referred to in Article 6(1) of Regulation (EU) 2024/1143

Class 1.5. Oils and fats (butter, margarine, oil, etc.)

4.2. Description of the agricultural product to which the registered name applies

The product designated “Huile d'olive Dir Béni Mellal” is an extra virgin olive oil that is obtained from healthy fruits, from Moroccan varieties namely Picholine marocaine (> 80%), Haouzia and Menara. The olive harvest takes place at the optimal stage of maturity, which corresponds to a maturity index ranging from 3.5 to 4.5, according to the IOC (International Olive Council) scale.

The olive oil presents sensory notes of pungent which vary from 2 to 4 on the organoleptic scale of the IOC. The fruity flavour is delicate or medium, with an intensity equal or greater to 2.0. The intensity of the bitter is less than or equal to 3.0 according to the IOC scale.

The “Huile d'olive Dir Béni Mellal” does not have organoleptic defects.

The characteristics of the oil are summarized in Table below:

Free acidity, expressed as % oleic acid	Peroxide value (mEq O ₂ /kg of oil)	Total polyphenols (mg/kg)
≤0.4%	≤15	>200

This physicochemical composition of the oil complies with the criteria for “extra” virgin olive oil, as defined by the regulations in force in Europe, inspired by the classification of the IOC.

4.3. Derogations on sourcing of feed (for products of animal origin designated by a Protected Designation of Origin only) and restrictions on sourcing of raw materials (for processed products designated by a Protected Geographical Indication only)

“Huile d’olive Dir Béni Mellal” is produced from olives or olive oils of the following varieties:

- Picholine marocaine accounting for at least 80 % in the groves covered by the designation of origin;
- Haouzia and Menara accounting for no more than 20 % in groves covered by the designation of origin.

4.4. Specific production steps to be carried out in the identified/defined geographical area

The Geographical Indication "Olive oil Dir Beni Mellal" represents an opportunity to increase the added value of local olive production. To fully leverage this Indication, olives must be collected and processed in the specified geographical area defined in point 5. This ensures that local producers can benefit from the added value generated by the product. It is essential to implement a documentary follow-up along with procedures for physical, chemical and sensory analysis to ensure comprehensive quality control from the harvesting of fresh olives, through the virgin olive oil extraction to the final packaging. These measures ensure adherence to quality standards and provide thorough monitoring at every stage of the process.

4.5. Specific rules concerning packaging, slicing, grating etc. of the agricultural product the registered name refers to

The containers of “Olive Oil Dir Beni Mellal” must protect the olive oil from light.

The maximum capacity of the containers is 10 liters.

The packaging of the oil takes place within the defined geographical area and is done in appropriate, food-grade containers, ranging from 0.1 liters to 10 liters.

The optimal use-by date is 18 months from the packaging date.

4.6. Specific rules concerning labelling of the agricultural product the registered name refers to

In addition to the compulsory information required by the rules on the labelling and presentation of foodstuffs, the labelling of oils bearing the designation of origin “Huile d’olive Dir Béni Mellal” must include the following:

- The mention of the "Protected Geographical Indication Olive Oil Dir Beni Mellal" or "PGI Olive Oil Dir Beni Mellal";
- The official logo of the protected geographical indication;
- The references of the Certification and Control structure.

These terms are displayed together within the same visual area on the label. They must be presented in clear, legible, and indelible characters of adequate size, making them prominent against the background and easily distinguishable from all other text and images.

5. Concise definition of the geographical area

The area of interest concerns the northern piedmont, where the landscape transitions from flat plains to mountainous terrain. This piedmont region, also known as the Dir, provides an ideal space for cultivating fruit and olive trees, which spread from the lower slopes into the plains. Its lush, permanent greenery is largely due to abundant water resources and fertile soils. A distinctive feature of the piedmont is its transitional zone between the Atlas Mountains and the Tadla plain. This inclined accumulation zone, a few kilometers wide, is shaped by the merging of alluvial fans that rest upon the detrital formations from the Mio-Pliocene period, forming the underlying bedrock of the plain. The Dir, particularly prominent north of Beni Mellal, is fed by water from the Atlas Mountains, either through springs or from the flow of the Jurassic aquifer beneath the alluvial deposits. Within this area, two distinct piedmont zones can be identified:

- The northern piedmont: is located in the province of Beni Mellal. It extends between Tisqui and Zaouïa Cheikh and benefits from abundant rainfall, and is the subject of our investigation.
- The southern piedmont is located in the province of Azilal. It benefits from significant rainfall but is lower than that of the northern piedmont.

The geographical production area of the “Olive Oil Dir Béni Mellal” is located in the foothills of Béni Mellal (North). The piedmont, considered the real Dir, is a narrow strip of fertile land in a transition position between the plain and the mountain. This brutal contact between a sloping terrain and the steep terraces which dominate it is developed over about forty kilometers in length and twenty kilometers wide in the South-West and is reduced towards the North-East.

The geographical area extends over the territorial communes of the Province of Beni Mellal.

The geographical area covered by the geographical indication "Olive Oil Dir Béni Mellal" extends over the Province of Béni Mellal and includes 8 municipalities and two parts of municipalities with six (6) douars and are as follows: Fom El Anceur, Taghzirt, Tanougha, Dir El Ksiba, El Ksiba, Ait Oum El Bekht, Zaouit Cheikh and Fom Oudi.

The two parts of municipalities with 6 douars:

- Five (5) Douars under the Béni Mellal commune (Ouled Draid, Somaa, Ain Asserdoun, Ourbia, Ait Said Ou Yechou Ait Boujou);
- A Douar (Gafay) belonging to the Oulad Yâich commune.

The geographical area of interest is located in the northern foothills of Beni Mellal province, in a piedmont, a transitional landscape between the Tadla plains and the Atlas Mountain range, also known as the Dir (Figure 3). The piedmont was shaped by the merging of alluvial fans resting over the Mio-Pliocene detrital formations from the Mio-Pliocene period, forming the underlying bedrock of the plain. It stretches for about 40 kilometers in length and varies in width, being about 20 kilometers wide in the southwest but narrowing towards the northeast. It is characterized by a lush, permanent greenery, sustained by abundant water resources and fertile soil, making it highly suitable for fruit and olive trees cultivation. It is nourished by water from the Atlas Mountains, either from springs or through the flow of the Jurassic aquifer beneath the alluvial deposits.

The geographical area extends across the territorial communes of the Béni Mellal province, covering a total olive-growing area of 2,940 hectares with a production potential

of 14,800 tons of fresh olives. It includes 8 municipalities and two parts of municipalities with a total of six douars (villages):

- **Municipalities:** Fom El Anceur, Taghzirt, Tanougha, Dir El Ksiba, El Ksiba, Ait Oum El Bekht, Zaouit Cheikh, and Fom Oudi.
- **Parts of municipalities:**
 - Five douars under the Béni Mellal commune: Ouled Draid, Somaa, Ain Asserdoun, Ourbia, and Ait Said Ou Yechou Ait Boujou.
 - One douar (Gafay) under the Oulad Yâich commune.

The names in Arabic of the communes and douars of the geographical area are as follows:

- Fom El Anceur: فم العنصر
- Taghzirt: تاكزيرت
- Tanougha: تانوغة
- Dir El Ksiba: دير القصيبة
- El Ksiba: القصيبة
- Ait Oum El Bekht: آيت أم البخت
- Zaouit Sheikh: زاوية الشيخ
- Ouled Draid, Somaa, Ain Asserdoun, Ourbia, Ait Said Ou Yechou and Ait Boujou in the municipality of Béni Mellal: أولاد ارضيوض، الصمعة، عين أسردون، أوربيع، آيت سعيد أويشو وآيت بوجو التابعين لإقليم بني ملال
- Gafay of Ouled Yaich commune: كفاي التابعة لجماعة أولاد ايعيش
- Fom Oudi: فم أودي

Figure 3. Territorial Communes within the Designated Geographical Area.

This geographical area is distinguished by a shared expertise in olive tree cultivation, harvesting, and olive crushing practices. It falls within the same Agricultural Territory.

6. Link with the geographical area

The Dir of Beni Mellal forms a distinct Agricultural Territorial Unti (TU3) due to its unique climate, relief and hydro-agricultural resources, thus creating a separate agro-ecological ecosystem.

The distinctive characteristics of the Dir of Beni Mellal olive oil are closely related to its pedoclimatic conditions, to the Moroccan Picholine olive variety, and its clones Menara and Haouzia. Moreover, local agricultural practices, such as cultivation techniques and oil extraction methods, also play a role, although to a lesser extent.

Located between the High Atlas Mountains and the Tadla plain, the Dir region is characterized by uneven terrain, with an average altitude of 580 meters (Photo 1). It stretches southward to Ain Asserdoun (723 meters) and northward into the plain at 480 meters (Hill Dir). The high-altitude cultivation of olive trees in this region imparts unique characteristics to the olive oil, particularly in terms of its fatty acid and polyphenol content. Olive oils from high-altitude groves are generally richer in phenolic compounds than those from lower altitudes (Osman, 1994; Ocakoglu, 2008). These compounds

contribute to the oil's complex flavor, provide antioxidant properties, and help increase its shelf life.

The richness of calcimagnesium soils in limestone imparts a firm texture to the fruit, which helps protect the oil from oxidation. Additionally, calcareous and nutrient-poor soils contribute to the oil's aromatic profile (Michelakis, 1992). Moreover, magnesium, an essential element in chlorophyll, also gives virgin olive oil its characteristic greenish color. Irrigation in the olive groves of the Piedmont area covers about three-quarters of the cultivated land and is mainly supplied by spring water, along with Small and Medium Hydraulics (PMH). The area's water resources come from numerous springs in the foothills of the Middle Atlas Mountains. According to Bamouh et al. (2012), the gravity-fed irrigation system used in the Dir region leads to a mild water deficit of 40 to 180 mm for mature olive trees (≥ 20 years old), a deficit that would be even higher if intercropping were considered. It is well-documented that water stress increases the phenolic content of olive oils (Tovar et al., 2001; El Antari et al., 2002; Patumi et al., 2002; Rotondi and Magli, 2004; Aganchich et al., 2008; Baccouri et al., 2009). Under conditions of water stress, the activity of phenylalanine ammonia-lyase (PAL) is enhanced (Patumi et al., 1999; Tovar et al., 2002).

Thanks to these distinctive factors, the International Olive Oil Council (IOOC) has recognized the virgin olive oil of the Béni Mellal province as one of Morocco's olive oils eligible for a distinctive sign of origin and quality (IOC, 2010).

On the basis of climate, relief and hydro-agricultural facilities, the Dir of Beni Mellal constitutes a separate Agricultural Territorial Unit (TU3) representing a distinct agro-ecological ecosystem.

The typicality of the Dir de Beni Mellal olive oil is closely linked to the geographical environment (relief, soil, climate), to the Moroccan Picholine olive variety and its clones Menara and Haouzia and, to a lesser degree, to the local know-how (cultivation management, oil extraction method).

Due to its location between the High Atlas and the Tadla plain, the Dir area is characterised by a generally uneven topography (average altitude 580m) (Photo 1). It extends to the south to the source of Ain Asserdoun (723m) and stretches to the north into the plain (480m) (Hill Dir). The olive tree cultivation at high altitude gives the olive oil a specific composition, particularly in fatty acids and polyphenols. Oils from olive groves located at high altitudes are richer in phenols than those from lowland olive groves (Osman, 1994; Ocakoglu, 2008). These compounds contribute to the overall complex flavour of olive oil, provide it antioxidant effects and are largely responsible for its shelf life. The richness of calcimagnesium soils in limestone gives the fruit a firm texture that protects the oil from oxidation. Furthermore, calcareous and lean soils give more aromatic oils (Michelakis, 1992). Magnesium, an element in the composition of chlorophyll, gives virgin olive oil a characteristic greenish colour. The irrigation of olive trees concerns $\frac{3}{4}$ of the olive grove of the Piedmont and is carried out by spring water and Small and Medium Hydraulics (PMH). The water resources of the area come from a multitude of springs in the foothills of the Middle Atlas Mountains. According to Bamouh et al (2012), the gravity irrigation mode, dominant in the Dir area, induces a slight deficit of 40 to 180 mm for old olive trees (≥ 20 years). This deficit would be more important if the presence of intercropping is taken into account. It is known that water stress induces

an increase in the content of phenolic compounds in olive oils (Tovar et al., 2001; El Antari et al., 2002; Patumi et al., 2002; Rotondi and Magli, 2004; Aganchich et al., 2008; Baccouri et al., 2009). Indeed, the activity of phenylalanine ammonia-lyase (PAL) is greater under water stress conditions (Patumi et al., 1999; Tovar et al., 2002).

In view of its typicality, the International Olive Oil Council (IOOC) has cited the virgin olive oil of the Beni Mellal Province among the Moroccan olive oils that can benefit from a distinctive sign of origin and quality (IOC, 2010).

2.2 Characterization of extra virgin olive oil samples from Morocco

The aim of the study was to assess the potential of Beni Mellal virgin olive oil, specifically from the *Picholine Marocaine* variety, for obtaining a Geographical Indication (GI), according to the European Union regulation. This process involves evaluating the quality and characteristics of the olive oil, which are closely linked to the specific geographical region of Beni Mellal in Morocco. The goal is to determine whether the oil meets the necessary criteria to be recognized as a GI under EU regulations, which would help protect its name and reputation, promote its quality, and provide economic benefits to the local producers. By achieving GI status, Beni Mellal virgin olive oil could gain access to premium markets, particularly in Europe, and contribute to the broader efforts to preserve traditional agricultural practices while ensuring product authenticity and traceability.

2.2.1 Materials and methods

2.2.1.1 Samples

The study analysed 15 virgin olive oil (VOO) samples from the 2023/2024 harvest season, with 80% of the samples derived from the "*Picholine Marocaine*" olive variety. All oils were produced using a two-phase extraction system without filtration. The samples were collected from five cooperatives— Abou Jami, Amhouach, Al Khair, Tamskourt, Colza (ABJ, AM, ALK, TS, and C)— with three samples taken from each cooperative.

2.2.1.2 Analyses

Basic quality parameters (free acidity, peroxide values, spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet) analyses were conducted in Meknès (ENAM) right after oil production and in Italy (UNIBO) after shipment by sea and truck under uncontrolled conditions.

Analyses conducted at ENAM:

- PV, free acidity, K_{268} , K_{232} (EU Reg. 2022/2105)

Analyses conducted at UNIBO

- PV, free acidity, FAME, K_{268} , K_{232} , and panel test (EU Reg. 2022/2105)
- Oxidation stability: Rancimat instrument
- Total phenols: Folin-Ciocalteu
- Phenolic compound analysis: HPLC-UV-VIS4
- Free radicals: 12 time points with microESR during 4 hours of sample heating at 80°C.

2.2.2 Results and discussion

2.2.1.1 Basic quality indexes

Table 1. Basic quality parameter results. The analyses have been performed by ENAM and UNIBO team, before and after shipment respectively.

	min - max	mean \pm s.d.	Eu Reg 2022/2105 *
Free Acidity (% oleic acid) ENAM	0.22 – 0.39	0.34 \pm 0.05	< 0.80
Peroxide Value (mEq O ₂ /kg) ENAM	9.14 – 10.65	9.75 \pm 0.45	< 20.0
Peroxide Value (mEq O ₂ /kg) UNIBO	11.7 – 16.8	14.5 \pm 1.5	< 20.0
K ₂₆₈ ENAM	0.12 – 0.16	0.14 \pm 0.02	< 0.22
K ₂₆₈ UNIBO	0.08 – 0.20	0.14 \pm 0.02	< 0.22
K ₂₃₂ ENAM	1.8 – 2.04	1.94 \pm 0.11	< 0.22
K ₂₃₂ UNIBO	1.76 – 2.35	2.05 \pm 0.13	< 2.50

All 15 virgin olive oil samples exhibited basic quality parameters within the limits established by EU Regulation 2022/2104 for extra virgin olive oils (Table 1).

2.2.1.2 Phenolic compounds

Table 2. Total phenols results, the analysis has been performed by UNIBO team. Results are expressed in mgGA/kg for results obtained with the Folin method and in mg/kg for results from HPLC determination.

	min - max	mean \pm s.d.
Phenols Folin (mg GA/kg) UNIBO	236.2 – 303.1	280.5 \pm 19.0
Phenols HPLC (mg/kg) UNIBO	301.8 – 426.0	360.7 \pm 34.6

Phenolic compounds were present in moderate quantities (Montedoro et al., 1992) (Table 2).

2.2.1.3 Fatty acid composition

Figure 4. Fatty acid composition (expressed as internal percentage) of the 15 virgin olive oil samples from the Beni Mellal geographical area (2023/2024 harvest season).

The fatty acid composition analysis revealed 12 distinct compounds (Figure 4), all of which comply with the thresholds set by EU Regulation 2022/2104 for extra virgin olive oils.

2.2.1.4 Oxidative state

Figure 5. Concentration of free radicals (expressed as µM of TEMPO) after 60, 80, and 240 minutes of kinetics.

Table 3. Oxidative Stability Index (OSI) results, the analysis has been performed by UNIBO team. Results are expressed as hours.

	min - max	mean ± s.d.
OSI (h) UNIBO	15.9 – 23.6	20.1 ± 2.3

The free radical levels showed notable variability across the samples, ranging between low and moderate concentrations, particularly after 220 minutes of heating at 80°C (Figure 5). OSI times

varied between 15 and 23 hours, reflecting a moderate resistance to oxidation. However, both the free radical levels and OSI times may have been impacted by shipment conditions, which could have influenced the oils' stability profiles (Table 3).

2.2.1.5 Panel test

Figure 6. Spider graphs showing the results of the sensory evaluation conducted using the panel test method on 15 samples of virgin olive oils from the Beni Mellal geographical area (2023/2024 harvest season).

The panel test classified 9 out of 15 oils as extra virgin, while the remaining 6 samples exhibited low-intensity defects, including fusty, rancid, and winey, and were therefore classified as virgin oils (Figure 6).

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Publication related to this research study

Zantedeschi, S., Tura, M., Valli, E., Barbieri, S., Bendini, A., Mokhtari, N., El-Mossaid, F. Z., Bajoub, A., Ait Elkassia, A., Ramanzini, E., Abidar, A., Oughad, A., Basidi, N., Setti, M., & Gallina Toschi, T. (2024). Unlocking the potential of Moroccan virgin olive oils for a possible recognition by the European Union's geographical indication through comprehensive analytical characterization of their quality and composition [Poster]. RAFA Conference, Prague, Czech Republic.

3. Teff flour

3.1 Protocol for a teff flour product specification and quality control for PGI/PDO protection under EU framework and labels for the valorisation of food products and identity

3.1.1 Single document

1. Name(s) [of Protected Designations of Origin (PDO) or Protected Geographical Indications (PGI)]

Ethiopian T'ef flour

2. Geographical indication type

PDO PGI

3. Third Country to which the defined geographical area belongs

Ethiopia

4. Description of the agricultural product

4.1. Classification of the agricultural product in accordance with the Combined Nomenclature heading and code, as referred to in Article 6(1) of Regulation (EU) 2024/1143

Class 1.6. Fruit, vegetables and cereals fresh or processed

4.2. Description of the agricultural product to which the registered name applies

T'ef (*Eragrostis tef* [Zucc.] Trotter) is a cereal with the smallest grain size, with a mass nearly 0.7 g/100 g of wheat grain which makes difficult to remove its bran. Hence, teff is processed to whole grain flour; as a result, its flour has a high fiber content (Alemneh et al., 2022). Teff is almost exclusively processed into whole-grain flour. Due to its small grain size, separating the bran and germ during milling is challenging. As a result, teff flour retains a higher proportion of germ, contributing to its greater nutrient content. Teff provides a well-balanced profile of essential amino acids and is a rich source of calcium and iron, which may explain the low prevalence of anemia in regions of Ethiopia where teff is regularly consumed. Because of the tiny dimensions of teff seeds, the whole meal flour is characterized by the presence of significant amounts of coating layers and sprout, resulting into high levels of insoluble polysaccharides.

Teff flour has been studied as a valuable ingredient to improve the quality of gluten-free products in several studies, mainly due to its superior nutritional quality (Do Nascimento et al., 2018).

It thrives across a wide range of agroclimatic conditions, particularly in mid-altitude and highland regions (1500–3000 m). The crop is typically cultivated in areas where the average annual rainfall ranges between 500 and 1200 mm, with temperatures varying from 15 to 25°C. Teff grows best in vertisols and heavy clay soils, with pH values between 6.2 and 8.5. Teff is considered a relatively pest-resistant crop, as its seeds can remain

viable for years without moisture and are naturally resistant to weevils and other storage pests, even without chemical treatments. However, fungal contamination by *Fusarium* and *Aspergillus* has been reported during both cultivation and storage, posing food safety risks due to their potential to produce mycotoxins. Traditional Ethiopian storage methods, often in humid conditions and in direct contact with soil, can promote fungal growth and mycotoxin contamination, leading to food spoilage. Limited studies have detected aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) and ochratoxin A (OTA) in teff, with average levels exceeding the EU regulatory limits by three-fold for AFB1 and seven-fold for OTA. Teff grains are rarely attacked by insect pests due to their tiny size, making the use of pesticides uncommon. The crop is also highly resilient to various environmental conditions, including waterlogging, further reducing the need for chemical treatments. However, teff can still become contaminated by pesticide residues from environmental sources. While the EU has set maximum residue levels (MRLs) to ensure food safety, no such regulations exist in Ethiopia. A study conducted on teff grains from the Jimma Zone detected pesticide residues, including cypermethrin, permethrin, endosulfan, and DDT, at levels exceeding Codex Alimentarius limits by up to 5.6 times.

Teff contamination with heavy metals is likely due to its small grain size, which increases soil contact, especially during traditional threshing methods using cattle hooves. Crop rotation and intercropping also contribute to contamination, as teff is often rotated with onion, bean, chickpea, and lentil, crops that may require fertilisers and pesticides. Residues from these chemicals can remain in the soil, affecting teff quality. To minimise heavy metal accumulation, farmers should avoid rotating or intercropping teff with crops that require high fertiliser use or are not pest-resistant.

Specific indications and standards for Teff flour are reported in the Ethiopian Standard ES 3880:2015.

Teff is vulnerable to adulteration along its supply chain. Various studies have detected common adulterants such as water, sugar, and starch in food products in Ethiopia (Adepoju et al., 2024). Teff grain color ranges from pale white to ivory white, light tan to dark brown, and even reddish-brown purple. In Ethiopia, the quality of teff is primarily assessed based on its color. The Ethiopian Standard Agency (ESA) recognizes four main color categories: very white (*magna*), white (*nech*), mixed (*sergegna*), and brown (*key*) teff. In Ethiopia, the color of the grain is not only an indicator of quality but also influences market demand and value. Very white and white teff command the highest prices and are typically consumed by wealthier individuals, while brown teff is sold at a lower price to low-income communities. The production area and soil type, which are closely related to grain color, significantly impact the market price of teff. For example, teff grown on black and brown soils produces brighter-colored grains, which are preferred by both consumers and traders, compared to those grown on red soils (Abewa et al., 2019).

The optimum date by which the flour may be used is 8 months from the date of milling; however, once opened, teff flour remains fresh for approximately two months. It is essential to store teff flour in a cool, dark, and dry place, in a sealed airtight container to preserve its freshness and quality.

4.3. Derogations on sourcing of feed (for products of animal origin designated by a Protected Designation of Origin only) and restrictions on sourcing of raw materials (for processed products designated by a Protected Geographical Indication only)

The varieties of teff that can be grown for the production of “Ethiopian T’ef flour” are as follows:

Quncho (DZ-Cr-387)

Felagot (DZ-Cr-442)

Tesfa (DZ-Cr-457)

Kora (DZ-Cr-438)

Dukem (DZ-Cr-425)

Dagme (DZ-Cr-43Bvarieties)

The above-mentioned varieties can be used individually or blended for the production of Ethiopian PGI teff flour.

4.4. Specific steps in production that must take place in the identified geographical area

The cultivation of the specified Teff varieties must take place in the designated geographical area.

4.5. Specific rules concerning packaging, slicing, grating etc. of the agricultural product the registered name refers to

Flour can be packaged in bags of 500 g, 1 kg, 10 kg, 25 kg, or 50 kg, and can also be delivered in bulk to any operator. The packaging does not have to be done solely by the miller.

4.6. Specific rules concerning labelling of the agricultural product the registered name refers to

The label must include the sales name along with the protected geographical indication, the milling lot identification, the net weight, the best before date, and the name or company name and address of the packager.

5. Concise definition of the geographical area

Teff is primarily cultivated in Amhara and Oromiya, which together accounted for up to 84% of the total cultivated area and production in 2011. Within these regions, East and West Gojjam (Amhara) and East and West Shoa (Oromiya) are the main production areas (Tadele & Hibistu, 2021). Amhara and Oromiya remain the dominant teff-growing regions, contributing 85.5% of the total cultivated area and 87.8% of production (Tadele & Hibistu, 2021). Smaller regions, such as Tigray and SNNP (Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples), contribute 6% and 9.6% of the cultivated area and production, respectively. Teff is mainly grown in the central regions of Ethiopia, where

favorable climatic and soil conditions support its cultivation. This hardy crop thrives at altitudes of up to 3,000 meters and is typically sown during the rainy season (May–June), with harvesting occurring about three months later (Abewa et al., 2019). The geographical area is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Geographical area concerned by Ethiopian T'ef flour PGI.

6. Link with the geographical area

In Ethiopia, teff is a major staple food and the country's most important crop in terms of cultivated area and production value (Tadele & Hibistu, 2021). Ethiopia is not only the largest teff producer but also the only nation where it serves as a staple crop (Tadele & Hibistu, 2022). It is widely grown across diverse agro-climatic conditions and plays a vital role in income generation, food security, and nutrition, supporting 6.5 million smallholder farmers (Tadele & Hibistu, 2021). Beyond its agricultural significance, teff is deeply embedded in Ethiopian culture. It is primarily used to make *injera*, a traditional fermented flatbread that forms the foundation of the Ethiopian diet. However, increasing global demand has driven up prices, making teff less affordable for low-income households (Bikila et al., 2024). The genetic diversity of teff is preserved by small-scale Ethiopian farmers, who continue to cultivate traditional varieties (Hager et al., 2012). However, climate change and water scarcity threaten this diversity, prompting scientists to seek new, more productive, and climate-resilient varieties (Woldeyohannes et al., 2020). Ongoing research focuses on improving teff yields and sustainability to support both domestic consumption and international markets (Ketema et al., 1997). Additionally, efforts are underway to develop value-added teff-based products, enhancing both its economic potential and nutritional benefits (Girma et al., 2013; Teshome et al., 2017).

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